

Research Article

Conceptual institutionalization in the process of socio-cultural translation and reproduction

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Abstract

The article considers the triad “enlightenment- upbringing-training” within the framework of the methodological scheme “thinking – communication – action”. It is argued that education itself is institutionalized in universities within and within the bachelor’s degree. Education is fundamentally different from training in the field of arts. Professional art training, the role of skill and creativity in professional art activity are specially considered.

Key words: Enlightenment, upbringing, training, education, training in the field of arts, art, skill, creativity

Introduction

The conceptual catastrophe that has lasted in Russian culture and mentality for more than a century is particularly severe in the sphere of socio-cultural transmission and reproduction, called education, enlightenment, professional orientation and training, so that neither students nor their teachers know what they are involved in and why, for what purpose, what

result they expect, or are they just stalling and killing time?

In order to make fundamental conceptual distinctions, it is suggested to use the methodological scheme of thought-activity proposed by M.G. Meerovich, which has become one of the basic schemes:

layers of think-activity	Institutional Processes in School
<p>thinking</p>	<p>enlightenment</p>
<p>think-communication</p>	<p>nurture</p>
<p>think- actions and interactions</p>	<p>learning</p>

Picture1. Layers of thinking-activity and institutional processes in school

Our activity in its entirety consists of three interpenetrated layers: the upper one is thinking, in the field of school institutional processes education corresponds to it; the middle one is thought-communication (respectively, education) and the lower one is thought-action (training). Education For more than two centuries, intermittently, it has been recognized that the main purpose of school (compulsory) education is enlightenment – this is exactly what this department was called and is called in the Russian Empire, in the USSR, and in the Russian Federation. Of course, this does not remove other functions from the school, for example, educational and teaching, but the family, the church and the so-called environment, the "street", the Internet and the media also participate in education along with the school [1]. In addition to school, various clubs, sections, clubs and other forms of additional education, cyclic, regular and short-term, participate in the training. Enlightenment is designed to form a worldview, first of all, as the backbone \ framework \ "skeleton" of the inner world of man.

Thinking activity in its totality represents three interpenetrating layers: the upper one is thinking, and in the sphere of school institutional processes it corresponds to enlightenment; the middle one is thought-communication (respectively, education); and the lower one is thought-action (learning).

Enlightenment

For more than two centuries, with interruptions, it has been recognized that the main purpose of school (compulsory) education is enlightenment - this is the name of this department in the Russian Empire, in the USSR, and in the Russian Federation. Of course, this does not remove from the school other functions, for example, educational and training, but in education, together with the school, the family, the church and the so-called environment, the "street", the Internet and the media are also involved [1]. In addition to school, various circles, sections, clubs and other forms of additional education, cyclical, regular and short-term, are involved in education.

Education is designed to form a worldview, first of all, as the backbone of a person's inner world.

Education is programmatic in the sense that it gives a bouquet of literacies: - linguistic literacy (the ability to write and read in native and foreign languages)

- mathematical literacy (counting, calculating estimates, budgets and expenditures, basic mathematical statistics and accounting, logic, numerical operation and combination, spatial orientation and imagination)

- legal literacy (the most serious, fatal problem, which has a thousand-year history of slavery and disenfranchisement, where the essence of law - justice - has been subjugated by law, governance and rule; it is legal illiteracy that prevents us from being among civilized nations, it is because of the absence of law as justice that we have unlawful and unjust courts and laws, the widespread practice of circumventing and violating our own and international laws, arbitrariness and violence, business and economy as a criminal enterprise, deeply echeloned and ineradicable corruption, total theft and ethical nihilism, legal chaos and disorder), if we manage to realize universal legal enlightenment, such monstrous and tragic distortions as presidential spying, Russian imperial fascism and colonialism will be historically eliminated - forever and ever.

- Computer literacy, including IT, telephony, robotics, etc.
- financial literacy
- transportation literacy, walking, wheeled non-motorized and motorized, water and air literacy
- sexual and genetic literacy
- spatial and temporal literacy (history and geography)
- ecological and biological literacy

- life literacy = ideas about right and healthy living (the physician god Asclepius and his daughters Cooking, Sanitation and Hygiene).
- Philosophical and thinking literacy
- musical literacy
- artistic and aesthetic literacy (all arts, including local and national)

Education should occupy at least half of all school time - both in terms of its importance and the fact that the school is practically a monopoly in education. For the sake of enlightenment it is even possible to increase the length of school life to 12-14 years instead of the current 9-11.

Nurture

If we talk about institutional (school) nurture, it should be oriented, naturally, to the social sphere:

- cultural, gender, racial, ethnic and religious loyalty and tolerance, tolerance of physical and mental deviations
- good-neighborliness and peacefulness, pacifism
- be nice
- rules and norms of behavior and communication
- attachment to the place/region/city of residence, its mores, customs, mythology and unique features (patriotism, understood as responsibility for one's native place, not unrequited and unrequited love for it)
- social autonomy and independence
- teamwork and collegiality, participativeness and cooperation
- asserting one's own interests and goal-setting, competitiveness
- building personal development trajectories

All this means the rejection of classroom organization, as well as the active learning of education, including games, simulations, imitations, simulators and trainings.

Learning

Schooling should have a user (user) orientation:

- housekeeping (cleaning, cooking, using household appliances, including electronic and electrical appliances, repairs, landscaping, etc.)
- caring for children, sick, elderly and infirm persons
- Possession of means of transportation, information and communication media
- ownership of computers, telephony and robots
- mastery of money and finances
- mastery of one's own body and psychosomatics (fitness, physical training, aerobics, dancing, sports).

One of the most important requirements for user (and only user) training is the integrativeness of all these skills and abilities (skills), because life activity itself is integrative, and also because they "support" each other and have reciprocity (mutual assistance and mutual influence).

Professional skills and abilities are not the prerogative of schools, but of the system of voluntary (non-mandatory, and therefore mostly paid) additional education.

Education

Strictly speaking, education proper begins after enlightenment, or with a slight overlap. Scholars claim that education takes 10,000 hours as a minimum and thus corresponds in duration to a bachelor's degree. Thus education is understood as:

- entering and mastering culture (culture-oriented education)
- becoming human in a person (humanistically oriented education) [3, 6].

University as the most common institutionalization of education (the most common is self-education) does not limit the educational process:

Picture 2. Binary process of education

In the course of education we change, but one step ahead is the change in our self-image, to which we aspire.

Education, like culture, is cumulative [4] and therefore we can only determine the level of education - from complete ignorance to a high level of education. In this sense, education is extensive and cannot be described by the characteristics of intensity. It is always one - unlike professions, which a person can have indefinitely many.

Professional training

Unlike education, vocational training can be carried out for an indefinitely long period of time, which depends on three major factors:

- A person's predisposition to the profession, professional suitability (a stutterer can be made a radio or television announcer, but it will take an unreasonably long time)
- the complexity of the profession itself (a pizza delivery man can be trained in 2-3 days, a surgeon - in several years)
- adequacy of training means - only playing chess will take a very long time to master the profession of a military strategist [5].

Professional training in most cases is not associated with education, so it can precede university education, for example, in college, or go in parallel (this is the case in about half of American universities), or complete education, for example, in a master's program [2].

In any case, professional training provides a minimum required level of professional competence, a minimum acceptable competitiveness, which is tested either by practice or by special tests/exams/standards. This,

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among other things, opens the floodgates of professional development. A special place is occupied by professional education, which allows a person not only to engage in professional activity, but also to transform/improve/develop/project it in prospective reflexion, and to teach it to others in retrospective reflexion.

We can distinguish several basic types of mastering professions:

- full-cycle professional education (multistage)
- primitive professional training (training)
- self-training
- apprenticeship in activity (in tandem with a mentor)
- self-discipleship in activity (without a mentor)
- life experience

In any of these trajectories there is a rather objective target-oriented criterion of professional growth - mastery. A master is not a slave of this or that craft, but someone who is fluent in it, a free man. A professional beggar and understudy cannot feel and be a free man.

Art: mastery and creativity. The riddle of creativity

Man is an artificial being, an art being, mastering himself and the world aesthetically, not only mentally and sensually. And any art is built on a combination of skill, acquired in the course of professionally organized activity, and creativity, an inner daring desire to overcome existing cultural norms and frameworks. Creativity cannot be imposed or instilled from the outside, it is always an inner impulse caused by the realization of one's own imperfection and the imperfection of the world. According to Plato, God created the world imperfectly so that man, struggling with this imperfection, to improve himself. After all, man is in the image of God, and therefore, by nature he is a creator. And this is the mystery of creativity, which in principle cannot be taught, except for some technical means, but which is required of everyone who is given talent, and talent is given to everyone.

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